

Preparation and characterization of floating polyelectrolyte complex beads for sustained release of metoclopramide hydrochloride

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Abstract

Metoclopramide hydrochloride (Met.HCl) has a short biological half-life and low oral bioavailability, which may limit its therapeutic efficacy. To address this, a novel gastroretentive floatable drug delivery system was developed with the aim of increasing stomach residence time and enabling prolonged drug release. Various formulations were prepared by mixing Met.HCl with alginate and olive oil to form an emulsion, which was then dropped into calcium chloride solution to produce beads, followed by surface coating with aminated chitosan to form a polyelectrolyte complex. Poloxamer 407 was subsequently incorporated at different concentrations to improve emulsion stability. The optimized formulation (F10), composed of alginate–chitosan–poloxamer 407 beads loaded with Met.HCl, exhibited entrapment efficiency exceeding 85%, buoyancy for more than 12 h without floating lag time, and sustained drug release reaching approximately 90% over 12 h. FTIR, DSC, and FE-SEM confirmed polyelectrolyte complex formation and supported the potential of this system for future *in vivo* evaluation.

Keywords

Alginate, chitosan, floating drug delivery, poloxamer 407, polyelectrolyte complex

Introduction

Oral administration is the most preferred method of drug delivery due to its ease of administration and high patient acceptance. However, incomplete drug absorption resulting from physiological variability remains a major challenge (Sen et al. 2023). An additional limitation arises from the short gastric residence time of conventional stomach-localized dosage forms (Lopes et al. 2016). This compromises the bioavailability and efficacy of the delivered drugs. This is especially critical for drugs with permeability-limited absorption that require longer upper gastric residence for effective permeation.

For instance, metoclopramide hydrochloride (Met.HCl) is classified as a class III drug according to the biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS) (Dahan et al. 2009). Classification as class III indicates high solubility and low permeability. The limited membrane permeability contributes to variable oral bioavailability, mainly due to extensive first-pass metabolism and individual physiological differences (Hamdi and Mohamed 2022). Clinically, Met.HCl is widely used in the management of nausea and vomiting, especially chemotherapy-induced emesis. However, its brief half-life of approximately 3–5 h necessitates frequent oral dosing of 20 mg four times daily for 2–4 days (Farooqi et al. 2020).

Therefore, gastroretentive approaches such as floating, expandable, mucoadhesive, and high-density systems have been developed to improve oral drug delivery, prolong drug release in the gastric region, and lessen the side effects of frequent dosages. Among these, floating systems are low-density systems that remain buoyant in gastric fluids, potentially allowing the drug to stay in the stomach for an extended period of time (Pawar et al. 2010). Many previously documented floating systems were developed as either single- or multiple-unit forms. Compared with single-unit forms, multiple-unit floating systems may reduce the variability associated with the “all-or-nothing” emptying process and provide uniform transit through the gastrointestinal tract. Several multiple-unit floating systems have been developed, including floating beads, hollow microspheres, and air-compartment multiple-unit systems (Chen et al. 2018).

Techniques have been developed to incorporate gas or oil into polymeric floating systems to provide buoyancy and enable prolonged gastric retention (Liu et al. 2024). Oil may offer an advantage over gas-generating approaches because it forms microscopic pockets within the matrix that support buoyancy (Khan et al. 2022). Its hydrophobic nature also acts as a barrier to drug diffusion and thereby prolongs release (Naiel et al. 2023). This retardation is more reasonably attributed to a physical matrix effect than to drug partitioning into the oil phase.

Floating beads were selected as the focus of this research because they are non-toxic, biocompatible, biodegradable, and widely accepted for use in food and pharmaceutical applications (Tønnesen and Karlsen 2002). Alginate is a naturally occurring anionic biopolymer that forms ionically cross-linked gels with multivalent cations such as Ca^{2+} , enabling its use in bead-based drug delivery systems (Lateef et al. 2024). However, beads' entrapment efficiency (EE) and prolonged drug release are major challenges when developing these beads to deliver hydrophilic medicines (Alazzo et al. 2024). Therefore, chitosan has been suggested as a coating polymer for beads due to its unique physicochemical properties and various potential applications. It is a cationic polymer produced by deacetylation of chitin. This process, deacetylation of chitin, hydrolyzes acetamide groups, generating free amino (NH_2) functional groups with the concomitant release of acetate ions (Iber et al. 2021). Alginate and chitosan have chemical characteristics that allow the creation of a polyelectrolyte complex through electrostatic interaction.

Chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte complex has attracted considerable interest as a versatile drug delivery platform because it can enhance the overall performance of polymeric delivery systems and allow formulation of dosage forms with pH-sensitive release. Alfatama et al. (2021) reported a core–coat bead system in which calcium-cross-linked alginate beads were coated with chitosan or chitosan oleate, resulting in improved bead robustness with reduced swelling and water uptake. Vaziri et al. (2018) also prepared alginate–chitosan complex beads reinforced by Na-tripolyphosphate

dual cross-linking and found smoother morphology, lower swelling, and better stability under simulated gastrointestinal conditions. In addition, Arora et al. (2011) incorporated Pluronic F127 (poloxamer 407, P407) into chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte complex nanoparticles and reported improved formulation outcomes, particularly enhanced drug entrapment efficiency. Collectively, these studies demonstrate the potential of chitosan–alginate polyelectrolyte complex systems as promising carriers for improving formulation stability and drug delivery performance. Such a system may also help address the limitations of Met.HCl by prolonging gastric residence and supporting sustained drug release. However, despite the availability of several gastroretentive systems for Met.HCl, including floating tablets (Singh et al. 2007) and gastroretentive films (Hamdi and Mohamed 2022), the application of alginate–chitosan polyelectrolyte complex beads as a gastroretentive delivery system for this drug has not yet been explored.

The current work aimed to develop a gastroretentive floating drug delivery carrier for Met.HCl based on a polyelectrolyte complex system composed of sodium alginate and chitosan. This system was further modified by incorporating oil as a hydrophobic buoyancy enhancer, while P407 was used as a stabilizing surfactant and may contribute to formulation effectiveness by improving emulsion stability. The study first describes the preparation and optimization of the developed system, followed by evaluation of buoyancy, entrapment efficiency, swelling behavior, *in vitro* drug release, and physicochemical characterization.

Experimental

Material

Met.HCl was purchased from Alkindi Pharmaceutical Company. Sodium alginate powder was purchased from Sino Pharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. (China). P407 was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Merck KGaA, Germany). Medium molecular weight chitosan powder was acquired from Glentham Life Science Ltd. (United Kingdom, UK). Calcium chloride was supplied by Beijing Jin Ming Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (China). Olive oil was purchased from Guoyao Chemical Co., Ltd. (Shanghai, China). Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was obtained from ACS Chemicals (Gujarat, India).

Methods

Formulation of floatable polymeric alginate-chitosan (ALG-CS) beads

There are two primary methods to prepare polyelectrolyte floating complex beads. In the first (one-step) method, the drug is mixed with sodium alginate. This dispersion is dropped into a solution containing chitosan and calcium chloride. In the second (two-step) method, the drug–alginate dispersion is first dropped into calcium chloride solution. The formed beads are then transferred into chi-

tosan solution (Luo and Wang 2014). Among these two methods, the two-step method was selected in the present study because it yielded the most favorable outcomes. Accordingly, 10 formulations of Met.HCl polyelectrolyte complex beads were employed experimentally, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Compositions of the developed floatable polymeric beads.

Formula code	Alginate (mg)	Chitosan (mg)	P407 (mg)	CaCl ₂ %	Olive oil (ml)
F1	50	150	–	1%	0.5
F2	100	200	–	1%	1
F3	150	150	–	1%	1.5
F4	200	100	–	1%	2.5
F5	200	100	50	1%	2.5
F6	200	100	100	1%	2.5
F7	200	100	150	1%	2.5
F8	200	100	200	1%	2.5
F9	200	100	150	1.5%	2.5
F10	200	100	150	2%	2.5

Volume used to dissolve chitosan was 10 mL of 2% acetic acid.

Volume used to dissolve the drug with sodium alginate and surfactant was 4 mL. A 10 mL volume of 1%, 1.5%, and 2% of CaCl₂ containing 100 mg, 150 mg, and 200 mg, respectively, was used as the cross-linker.

All the above formulations represent the amounts for a single dose of drug that correspond to 30 mg of Met.HCl to ensure sustained drug release and maintain therapeutic levels over an extended period.

Oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion was prepared using the emulsion gelation method. The aqueous phase was constituted by dissolving sodium alginate and drug in 4 mL of distilled water, followed by incorporation of olive oil as an oil phase. The mixture was subsequently ultrasonicated at 150 W for 10 min in an ice-water bath using a laboratory probe sonicator operating at 20 kHz and 75% amplitude in pulse mode (12 s on, 6 s off), with acoustic enclosure. The emulsification was carried out at a controlled temperature of approximately 37 °C. This step facilitated the formation of a stable emulsion prior to bead preparation. The emulsion was permitted to rest momentarily after sonication to verify uniformity and identify any phase separation (Chen et al. 2018).

Bead formation was carried out by dripping the emulsion into CaCl₂ solution through the ionotropic gelation method, followed by gelation, stirring, collecting, and washing. The produced emulsion was manually dripped through a 23-gauge needle into a cross-linking solution from a distance of 5–8 cm. Since the dropping rate may influence bead size and uniformity, the dripping process was performed as consistently as possible throughout the preparation. Different calcium chloride concentrations (1%, 1.5%, and 2% w/v) were selected to provide a graded increase in cross-linking density. This approach allowed systematic evaluation of its effect on bead formation, mechanical stability, and drug release characteristics, preventing insufficient or excessive gel hardening. When the droplets came in contact with the hardening bath, ionic gelation was induced, forming spherical beads. To avoid aggregation, the beads were gently stirred in the solution at a controlled speed of 50 rpm for 20 min to ensure complete bead formation while preserving bead integrity. The beads were collected using a sieve to maintain their shape and rinsed with deionized water to remove excess solution.

In this study, medium molecular weight chitosan was employed to create a polyelectrolyte complex with pre-prepared calcium alginate beads. The polymer proportions were defined as alginate:chitosan ratios of 1:3, 1:2, 1:1, and 2:1. Polymer ratios were selected after preliminary screening to obtain a stable emulsion, uniform mixing, and spherical beads with sufficient mechanical strength. A few drops of 1.25 M NaOH were added to chitosan solution to adjust the pH to 5. This adjustment increased the availability of free amino groups. The gelled beads were submerged in this pH-adjusted chitosan solution for approximately 30 min. The beads were rinsed three times with deionized water to remove excess chitosan, followed by drying at 40 °C for 6 h. The final chitosan-complexed beads loaded with Met.HCl had a consistent shape and were prepared for additional drug release and characterization research. Fig. 1 illustrates the complexed beads before and after drying.

Before drying

After drying

Figure 1. Floating beads before and after drying.

Formulation of floatable polymeric alginate–chitosan–poloxamer 407 (ALG-CS-P407) beads

The sodium alginate–olive oil–drug emulsion was supplemented with P407 at ratios of 4:1, 2:1, 4:3, and 1:1, which were selected to evaluate the effect of different polymer proportions on viscosity, emulsion stability, and properties of the prepared beads. All subsequent steps were identical to those used for the formulation of floatable polymeric ALG-CS beads without P407, respectively.

Evaluation of developed floatable polymeric beads

Analysis of floating ability

The formed polymeric bead's capacity to float was examined through visual inspection. Twenty precisely dehydrated polymeric beads were immersed in 900 mL of recently prepared simulated gastric fluid (SGF; pH 1.2). The experiment was carried out in a shaking-water bath at 37 °C and 50 rpm for 24 h. The floating duration of polymeric beads, also known as floating time, and floating lag time, also known as the time that the beads require for floating, were noted (Tang et al. 2007). The experiment was conducted in triplicate to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of the results.

Determination of polymeric bead size

For bead size analysis, a total of 28 beads were randomly selected and measured from two representative formulations, F4 and F5, one prepared before surfactant addition and the other after surfactant incorporation. The experiment was conducted in triplicate. The mean bead diameter was calculated and expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). This comparative approach was adopted to evaluate the influence of surfactant addition on bead size characteristics. Digital images of the polymeric beads were captured using a digital camera. The beads were placed against a dark background. A calibrated centimeter scale was included in each image for size reference. The bead size was determined using ImageJ software as the measuring instrument (Alazzo et al. 2024).

Assessment of entrapment efficiency

A mortar and pestle were used to break up a certain quantity of dried complex beads equivalent to 30 mg of Met.HCl. The resulting fragments were accurately weighed. The crushed beads were transferred to a beaker containing 100 mL of 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2). The mixture was maintained under magnetic stirring at 350 rpm and 37 \pm 0.5 °C for 2 h to allow complete swelling and drug release. The resulting solution was filtered using a 0.45 μ m syringe filter. An aliquot (1 mL) of the filtrate was diluted with 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) to obtain a final volume of 50 mL. The experiment was conducted in triplicate. The drug concentration was determined from the Met.HCl calibration curve equation by measuring absorbance at 309 nm (Abdel-Rahman et al. 2009). EE% was determined according to the following equation (Minkal et al. 2018):

$$EE(\%) = (C_i - C_f) / C_i \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where C_i is the initial concentration of Met.HCl given to the polymeric dispersion and C_f is the final concentration of the free drug identified in the filtrate, normalized to the weighted amount of loaded polymeric beads. The results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Swelling study

Using an immersion approach, the swelling behavior of all polymeric bead formulations was investigated. The mass of complex beads used in this experiment was equal to 30 mg of Met.HCl. The formulations were initially weighed (W_0). The beads were submerged in 900 mL of SGF (pH 1.2). The beads were withdrawn from the solution. They were gently wiped with filter paper to eliminate surface moisture and reweighed again (W_1) at predetermined intervals (15, 30, and 45 min; 1 h; and then hourly up to 12 h) (Sabar et al. 2011). The experiment was conducted in triplicate, and the results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The average swelling index values were calculated using the following equation:

$$Swelling\ ratio(\%) = \left[\frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \right] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

In vitro release study

The dissolution of Met.HCl was determined by dissolving the formulations in 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl at pH 1.2. The study was performed using a USP Type II dissolution device (paddle type, Copley dissolution 8000, Copley Scientific, UK) set at 50 rpm and 37 °C. Capsules were placed in the device jar for 12 h. At predefined intervals, 5 mL of each sample was withdrawn. A fresh dissolution medium of equal amount was added to the system. The samples were filtered through 0.45 μ m syringe filters and examined using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1650 PC, Japan) at 309 nm. The experiments were conducted in triplicate ($n = 3$) at each time interval, and the mean value was reported (Aziz and Sabar 2025). Formulations F1–F4 were used to investigate the effect of olive oil and changing the polymer concentration on the rate of drug release. Formulations F5–F8 were used to study the effect of changing surfactant concentration on drug release. The terminal set, F9 and F10, were used with different percentages of $CaCl_2$ (1.5% and 2%) to study the effect of enhancing the cross-linking agent on strengthening ionic interactions between sodium alginate and chitosan to create a strong drug-entrapment complex.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was performed on Met.HCl, chitosan, alginate, P407, olive oil, ALG-CS beads, ALG-CS-P407 beads, and ALG-CS-P407 beads loaded with Met.HCl (F10). For solid samples, small quantities were mixed with KBr and compressed into pellets, whereas in the case of olive oil, a small amount was applied directly onto KBr. The spectra were recorded over a wavenumber range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} , as described in the literature (Gajic et al. 2021).

Figure 2. *In vitro* floating behavior of polyelectrolyte complex beads.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was performed using a Mettler-Toledo DSC 820 apparatus. Chitosan, alginate, P407, Met.HCl, and ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (2–5 mg) were placed in 40 μ L aluminum crucibles. Heating was carried out from 0 to 300 $^{\circ}$ C at a rate of 10 $^{\circ}$ C/min. A nitrogen flow rate of 50 mL/min was maintained throughout the analysis (Dogaris et al. 2024).

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

A field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) was used to examine the morphological surface. Before the samples were attached to glass stubs using pre-applied double-sided glue, they were allowed to air dry. Thereafter, the stub was placed in a fine-coat ion sputter to deposit gold. An Inspect F50 SEM (Netherlands) was used to examine the surface morphology of the optimized formula (F10) at an accelerating voltage of 30 kV (Aziz et al. 2025).

Modeling of kinetic drug release

The Met.HCl cumulative amount released from the formulated polyelectrolyte complex beads at different time intervals was analyzed by employing zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models to determine the drug release mechanism (Paarakh et al. 2018).

Analytical statistics

The results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the level of statistical significance, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Result and discussion

Floating ability study

It was discovered that the developed formulations (F1–F10) did not exhibit any buoyancy lag time during this investigation. All formulations, regardless of the composition of the polymeric beads, remained buoyant in simulated gastric fluid for more than 24 h; therefore, no significant differences in floating behavior were observed among the formulations. The floating lag time was approximately 0 s for all formulations; therefore, the floating study was considered qualitative. The buoyancy was shown to be substantially correlated with the density of olive oil (0.91 g/cm^3), which

is less than the SGF value ($<1.004 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$). These outcomes additionally verified that the chosen polymer and oil concentrations were suitable for generating sufficient buoyancy (Naiel et al. 2023). Fig. 2 elucidates the *in vitro* buoyancy of polyelectrolyte complex beads.

Polymeric bead size

The comparison in Fig. 3 demonstrates the effect of emulsifier addition on bead morphology and size, highlighting the difference between formulations before and after the addition of the emulsifying agent (F4 and F5). It is evident that the addition of P407 increases the size of the ALG-CS beads. It acts as a polymeric thickener, increasing the solution viscosity. Higher viscosity prevents droplet disintegration during extrusion or dripping, resulting in larger droplets and, consequently, larger beads (Postolović et al. 2022). The average diameters of the prepared polyelectrolyte complex beads were $1.26 \pm 0.03 \text{ mm}$ for ALG-CS beads (Fig. 3A). The beads exhibited a relatively transparent appearance, which may suggest the presence of large oil droplets and incomplete emulsion uniformity. In contrast, ALG-CS-P407 beads loaded with Met.HCl (Fig. 3B) showed a large average diameter of $1.43 \pm 0.07 \text{ mm}$, with a turbid appearance. The change from transparency to turbidity may be attributed to increased light scattering caused by dispersed oil droplets. This is consistent with previous studies reporting improved emulsion characteristics with well-dispersed droplets (Alazzo et al. 2024). Nevertheless, this interpretation remains qualitative, and no definitive conclusions regarding emulsion uniformity or internal droplet distribution can be made based on the present data. The cross-linker solution concentration and hardening time did not significantly affect the size and aspect ratio of the produced beads. This

Figure 3. Bead size of A. ALG-CS beads; B. ALG-CS-P407 beads loaded with Met.HCl.

finding is consistent with prior work on *Lactobacillus acidophilus*-loaded alginate beads. This study reported that variations in calcium chloride concentration showed no discernible effect on bead size (Lotfipour et al. 2012).

Assessment of entrapment efficiency %

The findings presented in Table 2 demonstrate that the synthesized floating polyelectrolyte complex beads exhibited satisfactory entrapment efficiency, ranging from 55%–85%. In general, the loss of drug in the external phase makes encapsulating hydrophilic medications within spherical systems difficult and problematic (Yousry et al. 2019).

Table 2. Entrapment efficiency % in different capsule formulas ($n = 3$, mean \pm SD).

Formulations	EE% (mean \pm SD)
F1	55.67 \pm 1.43%
F2	59.83 \pm 2.30%
F3	66.46 \pm 1.85%
F4	69.70 \pm 1.12%
F5	75.15 \pm 1.90%
F6	65.13 \pm 2.10%
F7	76.58 \pm 1.75%
F8	71.87 \pm 1.63%
F9	75.15 \pm 2.05%
F10	85.07 \pm 1.98%

The increase in the volume of olive oil enhanced entrapment efficiency. This observation is compatible with the previous study on clarithromycin mucoadhesive alginate beads, where higher oil content resulted in greater drug incorporation (Adebisi et al. 2015). The improved entrapment efficiency may be attributed to the formation of a larger polymer–oil interface. This interface was effective in preventing the drug from diffusing into the external aqueous phase during cross-linking. Chitosan concentration plays a critical role in determining the entrapment efficiency. The higher chitosan concentration was associated with reduced entrapment efficiency. This observation aligns with a prior study on the diclofenac sodium polyelectrolyte complex system (Nikolova et al. 2022). This study reported lower drug content at elevated chitosan levels. The lower EE% observed at higher chitosan concentrations may be explained by the higher viscosity of the chitosan coating solution, which could affect the formation of the outer layer during coating and drying. This may result in a less dense and more porous outer layer, allowing greater drug leaching during the coating and washing steps. Additionally, the polymer mixing ratio (ALG-CS) affected the entrapment efficiency. The ratio 2:1 caused higher encapsulation effectiveness. This is attributed to more favorable polymer–polymer interactions. In contrast, increasing chitosan concentration beyond this ratio could reduce the degree of cross-linking between alginate and calcium chloride. As a result, this facilitates leakage of the drug from the beads (Shi et al. 2006). This

effect was associated with the distinct structure observed in formulation F4 compared with other formulations.

In ALG-CS beads, the encapsulation of Met.HCl was improved by the addition of P407. A considerable variation in the EE% values, from 69% to 75%, of floating polyelectrolyte complex beads made with and without surfactant was noted. This evidence agrees with a previous study that intended to increase the encapsulation of curcumin in alginate–chitosan–Pluronic F127 composite nanoparticles for delivery to cancer cells (Das et al. 2010). This enhancement may be due to greater accommodation of drug molecules within the micellar or polymeric network. This effect supports the observed improvement in drug entrapment efficiency.

The excessive amount of P407 has been observed to migrate from the beads in the calcium chloride medium during preparation. Consequently, increased drug diffusion from the beads into the cross-linking solution led to a reduced degree of drug incorporation. This finding was in line with the preceding research that aimed to incorporate curcumin into a hydrogel system composed of three biocompatible polymers— κ -carrageenan, sodium alginate, and poloxamer. That study reported reduced drug encapsulation with a higher amount of P407 (Postolović et al. 2022). The increase in calcium chloride concentration enhanced entrapment efficiency. This result was consistent with the previous study that reported the development of a prolonged-release dosage form of trimetazidine dihydrochloride (TMZ). The study showed that an increase in calcium chloride as a cross-linking agent promoted alginate gelation. The gelation led to the formation of calcium alginate beads that entrapped a high quantity of TMZ (Mandal 2010). Comparable findings have been reported in diazepam alginate intravaginal beads, where an increase in the proportion of cross-linker from 1% to 2% resulted in higher entrapment efficiency (Sabry 2018).

To validate these findings statistically, the entrapment efficiency was analyzed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. The analysis revealed a highly significant difference among formulations ($p < 0.0001$). Tukey's multiple comparisons confirmed that formulation F10 exhibited significantly high entrapment efficiency compared to all other formulations ($p < 0.0001$), while no significant difference was observed between formulations F1 and F2 ($p > 0.05$). These observations support the previously discussed effects of olive oil content, polymer ratios, surfactant concentration, and cross-linking level on drug entrapment efficiency.

Swelling study

The swelling behavior of all formulations is presented quantitatively in Fig. 4. Differences among formulations were observed over time and may be related to variations in formulation composition. The prepared beads maintained their structural integrity during the swelling experiments. It is well recognized that hydration of the hydrophilic groups of both alginate and aminated chitosan derivatives is primarily responsible for the swelling of the

dry polyelectrolyte complex beads (Hoffman 2012). The formulations F1–F4 showed a gradual increase in swelling ratio with time, reaching maximum values at approximately 8–10 h. The peak swelling ratios were approximately 95% for F1, 100% for F2, 98% for F3, and 103% for F4, followed by a slight decrease at 12 h, as presented in Fig. 4A.

In fact, the interpolymer complex is broken down at approximately pH 1.2. The aminated chitosan component primarily controls the overall swelling behavior. It is indeed soluble at low pH values. This solubility is coupled with strong electrostatic repulsion arising from the protonation of the NH_2 groups to NH_3^+ . These effects promote expansion of floating polyelectrolyte complex beads, leading to enhanced swelling (Omer et al. 2016). However, the extent of swelling remained controlled because the alginate polymer exhibits limited swelling in an acidic environment. Under these conditions, the carboxyl ($-\text{COOH}$) groups of alginate remain unionized; as a result, charge repulsion is minimal, which limits bead porosity and swelling (Bajpai and Sharma 2004). In addition, the presence of olive oil fur-

ther limited water penetration, thereby reducing swelling capacity. Nevertheless, limited swelling still occurred due to water seeping through surface pores, where the absorbed water hydrates the hydrophilic groups and leads to an increase in bead weight (Patel et al. 2016). At later time points, a decline in swelling may be attributed to partial erosion or dissolution of the swollen polymer matrix. Overall, the swelling ratio of the beads was reduced upon the addition of P407. The formulations F5–F8 also showed time-dependent swelling, with maximum values reached at approximately 6–8 h. The highest swelling ratios were approximately 95% for F5, 90% for F6, 100% for F7, and 78% for F8, after which the values gradually declined, as illustrated in Fig. 4B.

This behavior was attributed to hydrogen bond formation between P407 and the carboxylate group of alginate. Additionally, hydrogen bonds occur between chitosan and these groups, contributing to this effect. As a result, polymer–water interactions become restricted, and swelling is hindered (Chun et al. 2003). However, it is considered negligible as the beads remain swollen and undergo shrinkage only after 6 h. Moreover, as the proportion of P407 increased within the optimal range, its hydrophilic and water-soluble qualities may encourage water absorption into the calcium alginate beads (Khlibsuwan et al. 2020). The formulations F9 and F10 showed increased swelling followed by a slight decrease at later time points. As shown in Fig. 4C, the maximum swelling ratio reached approximately 106% for F9 and 95% for F10. This reduction may be attributed to the increase in CaCl_2 concentration, which enhanced cross-linking within the beads and thereby lowered their swelling capacity. Consequently, this effect may contribute to prolonging drug release for several hours (Straccia et al. 2015).

Figure 4. Swelling behavior of the formulated polyelectrolyte complex beads. **A.** ALG-CS beads; **B.** ALG-CS-P407 beads; **C.** After increasing the percentage of cross-linking agent in ALG-CS-P407. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

In vitro release

The formulations F1, F2, and F3 released the drug completely within 5, 7, and 8 h, respectively. The corresponding sodium alginate–chitosan mixing ratios were 1:3, 1:2, and 1:1. In contrast, formulation F4, prepared with higher alginate content (2:1), exhibited a considerably prolonged drug release profile, with release extending up to 9 h, as illustrated in Fig. 5A. The sustained release behavior of F4 may be attributed to the formation of a stiffer, alginate-rich gel matrix in the release medium. This matrix shows reduced swelling compared to chitosan-rich beads, thereby limiting aqueous channel formation and slowing drug diffusion. This observation was consistent with Shu and Zhu (2002).

However, the cumulative drug release from all these formulations remained relatively low during the initial 2 h, ranging from 13%–17%, and reached only 19%–25% at the end of the release period. The drug release rate was enhanced by incorporation of P407 as a surfactant (Fig. 5B). Accordingly, four formulations (F5, F6, F7, and F8) were prepared to investigate the effect of surfactant concentration on drug release from the polyelectrolyte complex beads. Formulation F5 showed a relatively higher initial release, with 34% of the drug released within the first 3 h. For F6, cumulative drug release was 28.85% within the

Figure 5. Release behavior of Met.HCl from formulated polyelectrolyte complex beads. **A.** ALG-CS beads; **B.** ALG-CS-P407 beads; **C.** After increasing the percentage of the cross-linking agent in ALG-CS-P407. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

first 2 h, with release completion at 8 h reaching 44%. F7 exhibited a higher release profile, with approximately 49% released within the first 2 h and 87% released after 12 h. In contrast, F8 showed a lower initial release of 19.4% during the first 2 h and completed drug release within 9 h, achieving a total release of 30.1%. Among all formulations, F7 was selected for further consideration based on its relatively higher release extent over 12 h compared to other formulations. However, a noticeable initial burst release was observed during the first 2 h. The concentration of calcium chloride was increased to minimize the initial burst effect. Fig. 5C illustrates the influence of cross-linking concentration on the release profile of Met.HCl from prepared polyelectrolyte complex beads. Based on these findings, formulations F9 and F10 were developed to evaluate this effect more thoroughly. Formulation F9 exhibited approximately 32% drug release within the first 2 h and cumulative release of 88.9% over 12 h. F10 demonstrated a significantly more delayed release, with 27% released in

the initial 2 h and 90% at the end of 12 h. The delayed release observed in formulations F9 and F10 may be attributed to the increased cross-linking density resulting from higher calcium chloride concentration. This effect is expected to enhance the rigidity of the polymeric matrix and reduce drug diffusion. Additionally, partial complexation between calcium ions and alginate carboxylate groups may induce rearrangement of the polyelectrolyte chains, contributing to improved structural stability (Dautzenberg and Kriz 2003).

Kinetics of drug release

The dissolution data of the various formulations (F4, F7, F9, and F10) were assessed using several kinetic models. This analysis was performed to determine the *in vitro* drug release behavior, as presented in Table 3. When the drug release kinetics were examined using the Higuchi model, all formulations showed high correlation coefficients. These results indicate that diffusion through the polymeric matrix is the predominant mechanism governing drug release. F4 and F10 had particularly high Higuchi R^2 values, indicating a diffusion-controlled release mechanism. According to the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, the calculated release exponent (n) values ranged from 0.440 to 0.647. These exponent values provide insight into the underlying release mechanisms. Formulation F4 had release behavior consistent with near-Fickian diffusion, whereas formulations F7, F9, and F10 showed anomalous non-Fickian transport. These findings suggest that drug release from the studied formulations is primarily governed by diffusion, with polymer relaxation. This release pattern is consistent with the swelling study, since swelling of the chitosan-containing matrix in acidic medium can promote polymer-chain relaxation after hydration, thereby facilitating the diffusion of dissolved drug through the relaxed matrix. Thus, the release mechanism in these formulations is interpreted as the combined contribution of diffusion and swelling-controlled relaxation (Vigata et al. 2020).

Selection of the optimal formula

ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (F10) demonstrated high entrapment efficiency, reaching approximately 85%; a significantly more delayed release, with 27% released in the initial 2 h and 90% at the end of 12 h; an appropriate swelling profile; and favorable buoyancy behavior.

Therefore, F10 was selected as the most suitable formulation for further characterization based on its overall performance.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

The spectrum obtained from FTIR is a reliable analytical technique to evaluate the purity of drugs and polymers. It helps to validate drug–polymer and polymer–polymer interactions. In addition, FTIR is used to confirm complex formation, as presented in Fig. 6. Chitosan exhibited bands

Table 3. Release kinetics parameters of formulations.

Formulation	Zero-order K_0 (min^{-1})	Zero-order R^2	First-order K_1 (min^{-1})	First-order R^2	Higuchi K_H ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{min}^{1/2}$)	Higuchi R^2	Korsmeyer–Peppas K_{kp} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{min}^{-n}$)	Korsmeyer–Peppas R^2	n
F4	2.75	0.5068	0.033	0.6136	8.213	0.932	9.245	0.942	0.440
F7	14.144	0.528	0.258	0.831	29.77	0.9119	30.46	0.912	0.481
F9	11.68	0.881	0.184	0.966	6.71	0.822	21.76	0.994	0.604
F10	10.28	0.895	0.149	0.973	21.86	0.965	17.89	0.997	0.647

at 3466 cm^{-1} and 3302 cm^{-1} (O-H and N-H₂ stretching), 1654 cm^{-1} (C=O amide I band), 1593 cm^{-1} (N-H bending and amide II band), and 1153 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching) (El-haes et al. 2024). The spectra of natural alginate show absorption bands at 3406 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the stretching vibration of O-H groups, while 2929 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching frequency of C-H groups. The characteristic functional groups of alginate, particularly the asymmetric stretching of (-COO-), create a large asymmetrical band at 1633 cm^{-1} . In addition, the bands observed at 1080 cm^{-1} and 1024 cm^{-1} are assigned to C-O-C stretching vibrations, which are associated with the uronic acid residues of alginate (Sun et al. 2019). The IR spectra of P407 show absorption peaks at 2887 cm^{-1} (C-H stretch aliphatic), 1342 cm^{-1} (in-plane O-H bend), and 1109 cm^{-1} (C-O stretch) (Vyas et al. 2009). The FTIR spectrum of Met.HCl shows a symmetric N-H stretching vibration observed at 3305 cm^{-1} . The peaks observed at 3392 cm^{-1} and 3194 cm^{-1} were assigned to amide group N-H asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations. The carbonyl stretching vibration of the C=O group appeared at 1633 cm^{-1} for amides. The IR spectrum of Met.HCl is further characterized by absorption peaks at 2939 cm^{-1} (for C-H stretching vibration in the aromatic ring), 1597 cm^{-1} (for N-H bending vibration), 1211 cm^{-1} and 1080 cm^{-1} (for asymmetric and symmetric C-O stretching vibration of the -OCH₃ group), 1321 cm^{-1} (for aromatic -C-N stretching vibration), and 593 cm^{-1} (for C-Cl stretching vibration) (Barman et al. 2018). In the FTIR spectrum of olive oil, bands at 3105 cm^{-1} are attributed to the stretching vibration of (=C-H) groups. The stretching vibrations of methylene (-CH₂-) and methyl (-CH₃) groups can be observed at frequencies of 2922 and 2853 cm^{-1} , respectively. The bending vibrations of methylene and methyl groups are recorded at 1465 cm^{-1} and 1377 cm^{-1} . The strong absorption band at 1740 cm^{-1} is caused by (C=O) double-bond stretching vibration. C-H deformation and bending, as well as C-O stretching vibration, produce peaks in the $1500\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ area (Rohman and Che Man 2012). The FTIR spectrum of ALG-CS-P407 revealed a peak at 1447 cm^{-1} (salt of the carboxyl group), indicating an ionic connection between the two reactive groups (Arora et al. 2011). The peak at 1375 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-H bending of P407 (Das et al. 2010). The IR spectrum of ALG-CS-P407 beads loaded with Met.HCl elucidates a prominent peak approximately 1560 cm^{-1} , indicating the production of polyelectrolyte complexes by the NH₃⁺ group (Naiel et al. 2023). Furthermore, the typical absorption peaks of Met.HCl are still evident in the polymeric beads, although slightly broader and less intense.

Figure 6. FTIR spectra of olive oil, alginate, chitosan, P407, Met.HCl, ALG-CS, and ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (F10).

These results demonstrate that there was no chemical interaction between the drug and the alginate and chitosan biopolymers during bead production (Angadi et al. 2012).

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC thermograms of the separate components and their combinations are presented in Fig. 7. Pure Met.HCl revealed two endothermic peaks at $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $184\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. A small exothermic peak was also observed at $105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The endothermic peak at $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was attributed to drug dehydration. The peak at $184\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was related to the melting of the drug. These findings suggest that Met.HCl may undergo amorphization after dehydration and subsequently recrystallize at elevated temperatures (Lin 2015). The DSC thermogram of pure chitosan showed an endothermic peak at $85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This peak corresponds to water evaporation. A strong exothermic peak was observed at approximately $280\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This peak indicates the progressive degradation of chitosan (El-Gawad et al. 2012). The melting point of P407 is $57.69\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Dugar et al. 2016). The DSC thermogram of pure alginate showed an endothermic peak at $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This peak suggests water loss due to the hydrophilic nature of alginate. Additionally, an exothermic peak was observed at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This peak indicates thermal degradation of the alginate polymer (Alkhatib et al. 2022). The DSC thermogram of ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (F10) was examined. The characteristic exothermic peaks associated with chitosan and alginate at $280\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ disappeared. A new exothermic peak at $270\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ emerged. The creation of a polyelectrolyte complex is confirmed by such thermal behavior, which reflects intermolecular interactions between the two polymers (Sarmiento et al. 2006). Additionally, the shift of the drug melting peak to a lower temperature indicates loss of crystallinity toward an amorphous state (Jelić 2021).

Figure 7. DSC of alginate, P407, chitosan, Met.HCl, and ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (F10).

Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

The optimal formula, ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl (F10), shown in Fig. 8, was subjected to morphological examination using FE-SEM. The results revealed a relatively porous surface morphology. This structure may facilitate fluid penetration into the beads, which could contribute to swelling and influence drug release behavior (Huang et al. 2012); nevertheless, as FE-SEM analysis is limited to surface morphology, these images do not provide direct information about the internal structure of the formulation. Further characterization would be required to provide more detailed insight into internal structure and component distribution.

Figure 8. The FE-SEM of the ALG-CS-P407 loaded with Met.HCl.

Limitation of the study

The main limitation of this study is that the evaluation of the developed gastroretentive polyelectrolyte complex beads was restricted to simplified *in vitro* experiments. These findings may not fully reflect the complex and dynamic physiological conditions of the human gastrointestinal tract. These conditions include variations in gastric motility, pH, fed or fasted states, enzymatic activity, mechanical stress, and inter-individual variability. All these factors may influence gastric retention and drug release behavior *in vivo*. Consequently, the predictive value of the *in vitro* findings for *in vivo* performance remains limited. The actual therapeutic efficacy of the formulation cannot be fully established based solely on the current experimental design. Therefore, further investigation using biorelevant dissolution models, animal studies, and well-designed *in vivo* experiments is necessary. They are also needed to confirm sustained drug release behavior and clarify bioavailability and pharmacokinetic performance. This will strengthen the translational relevance of the developed formulation.

Conclusion

This study investigated the development of polyelectrolyte complex beads to improve the gastroretentive delivery of Met.HCl. Various bead formulations were prepared from a mixture of Met.HCl, sodium alginate, and olive oil by dropping the formed emulsion into calcium chloride solution. The resulting beads were then introduced into chitosan solution to produce polyelectrolyte complex beads. Poloxamer 407 was incorporated into the formulation to improve emulsion stability and enhance overall formulation performance.

In different weight combinations, the optimized formulation (F10) was prepared using 200 mg alginate, 2.5 mL olive oil, 150 mg poloxamer 407, 100 mg chitosan, and 2% calcium chloride. This formulation resulted in improved entrapment efficiency exceeding 85%, buoyancy for more than 12 h, and sustained drug release reaching approximately 90% over 12 h.

The improved performance was attributed to the combined effects of olive oil, poloxamer 407, and the interaction between alginate and chitosan, which formed a float-

ing polyelectrolyte complex system capable of retarding drug release under acidic conditions. These findings highlight the potential of this system as an enhanced floating delivery system for Met.HCl. Further *in vivo* studies are needed to confirm gastric residence time, bioavailability, and therapeutic performance.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

All authors participated in structuring and planning the study. Tasnim Ali Mahsun executed material preparation, collection, and analysis of information, as well as Methaq Hamad Sabar supervised every phase of the inquiry, including the drafting of paper. All authors examined and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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